

Statistical States and Their Relationship to Constraints

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Probabilities in statistical mechanics are often considered as being proportional to the number of states available, subject to certain constraints. For example, for a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas of N particles with total energy E , one considers the various arrangements associated with distributing E among the N particles, namely $N! / \text{Product over } i n(e_i)!$ where $n(e_i)$ is the number of particles with energy e_i . The constraint is $\text{Sum over } i e_i n(e_i) = E$, i.e. one relaxes the constraint that the energy of the N particles adds to E and replaces it with the condition of average energy adding to E . (One then maximizes the \ln of the number of states subject to the constraint.). This is a common procedure.

The point we wish to make is that in the above situation, the number of states (used to calculate probability) is automatically associated with the constraint on energy. In other words, one counts the number of states associated with energy distribution. This seems straightforward in the above example, but even in this case, the resulting MB distribution $C \exp(-e/T)$ is summed over a different counting mechanism, namely one associated with counting momentum states, i.e. $C \int dx dy dz$.

We argue that there may be ambiguity in defining the number of states in a problem and that this may lead to different probability distributions. In particular, we consider a gas of n particles moving in 1-dimension, such that: $\text{Sum over } i p(i)p(i) = RR$ where $E = RR/2m$. This is a constraint equation associated with energy. If the n th particle has momentum $p(n)$, then: $\text{Sum over } i=1, n-1 p(i)p(i) = RR - p(n)p(n)$. In (1), the probability $P(p(n))$ is said to be proportional to the surface area of the $n-1$ sphere, as allowable p vectors ($n-1$ dimensions) touch this surface. Thus, states are being counted in terms of momentum and this ultimately leads to a probability $P(p)dp = dp C (E - pp/2m)^{\text{power}((n-3)/2)}$.

In (2), states are counted using energy and this leads to $P(e)$ proportional to $(E-e)^{\text{power}(n-2)}$. In the large n limit, one has $(E-e)^{\text{power}(n/2)}$ versus $(E-e)^{\text{power}(n)}$. In other words, counting states in two different ways leads to two different probability expressions. As a result, counting states does not seem to be so straightforward. We argue that there must be a criterion for counting states and suggest they are counted with respect to the constraint. The constraint for the gas is in terms of energy and so the states should represent allowable energy configurations. This in turn follows from $d \text{Sum over } i=1, n e_i = dE=0$. $De_i = d pp/2m = p/m dp$ which is not the same as dp which would be used to count momentum states. Thus, the counting of the appropriate type of states seems to be important.

Counting of States

It may at first seem that the counting of states in a problem should be obvious, but states are counted on the basis of identifiers. If one uses one kind of identifier, one may count states in one way, while a different identifier leads to the counting of different states. Different counts represent different probabilities. This approach does not only apply to physics, but to the social sciences where one sees tables with percentages (i.e. probabilities) based on the identifiers chosen. In other words, the probability may depend on the identifier used. If constraints appear

in the problem, these apply to specific identifiers and so we argue that the states should be counted with respect to these identifiers. This removes the ambiguity of counting states and leads to a unique probability distribution.

Traditional Maxwell-Boltzmann Gas

A Maxwell-Boltzmann gas is often presented in the following way. One considers N particles with a total energy of E . One then tries to express the number of arrangements (related to the distribution of E , the constraint or identifier), i.e.:

$$\text{Number of states} = \frac{N!}{\prod_i n(e_i)!} \quad ((1))$$

Here $n(e_i)$ is the number of particles with energy e_i . As a result, one counts states in terms of the constraint variable energy without even thinking of it, because energy is the only identifier which seems to be present in the wording: N particles with total energy E .

One next takes \ln of ((1)) and maximizes, subject to the constraint $\sum_i e_i n(e_i)$. This relaxes the rule that the sum of energies is E and replaces it with the condition that the average energy is E . In such a case, each particle may have energy from 0 to infinite.

In this example, there is only one identifier (energy) and so there is no ambiguity as to how one should count states. We suggest, however, that the ambiguity of counting states is already present. There is no issue in counting states based on energy in ((1)), but when one sums over e_i states, i.e. using $P(e) = C \exp(-e/T)$, one switches to the identifier momentum and counts momentum states. In three-dimensions:

$$1 = \int C \, dp_x \, dp_y \, dp_z \, \exp(- (p_x^2/2mT + p_y^2/2mT + p_z^2/2mT)) \quad ((2))$$

Thus, there are two ways to count states, one using energy and the other using momentum vectors. The energy approach is used to determine $\exp(-e/T)$ because it is associated with the constraint on energy, we argue. We suggest one has to be careful as to what states are counted when trying to derive probability.

Maxwell-Boltzmann Gas and Momentum Spheres

In (1), a gas of n particles with one-dimensional motion is described by the constraint:

$$\sum_{i=1, n} p(i)p(i) = RR \quad \text{where } E = RR/2m \quad ((3))$$

Here $p(i)$ is the momentum of the i th particle (it has only one component of momentum).

((2)) is a constraint on energy, but is written in terms of the variable momentum.

Consider the n th particle having $p(n) = \text{constant}$. Then ((3)) becomes:

$$\sum_{i=1}^{n-1} p(i)p(i) = RR-p(n)p(n) \quad ((4))$$

This describes an n-1 sphere and (1) argues that probability is proportional to the surface area of the n-1 sphere. This, however, involves counting p (momentum states) and not energy states.

The result of (1) is ultimately:

$$P(p)dp = dp C (E - pp/2m)^{\text{power } \{ (n-3)/2 \}} \quad ((5))$$

$$\text{In the high } n \text{ limit, probability is proportional to: } (E-e)^{\text{power } n/2} \quad ((6))$$

Counting Energy States

In (2), an alternative approach to counting states is presented, namely one based on energy. It is suggested that:

$$P(e) \text{ is proportional to } (E-e)^{\text{power } (n-2)} \quad ((7))$$

To see this result, consider $n=4$. The fourth particle has energy e , so there is $E-e$ energy left. It may be distributed to particles 2 and 3, as the remaining energy may be associated with particle 4. The probability is associated with product states of particles 2 and 3, based on energy, i.e.:

$$\text{Number of states is proportional to: } \int_0^{E-e} de_2 \int_0^{E-e-e_2} de_3 \quad ((8))$$

This approach ultimately leads to ((7)). In the high n limit, ((7)) yields $(E-e)^{\text{power } n}$ which differs from ((6)).

As a result, we argue that in a given problem one may count states in different ways. The above shows that counting momentum versus energy states leads to different results.

States Based on Constraints

In order to resolve the issue of counting states, we suggest that they should be counted based on the constraint involved. For example:

$$E = \sum_i e_i \quad ((9))$$

$$dE = \sum_i de_i \quad ((10))$$

If one has a set of $\{e_i\}$ which satisfies ((9)) and wishes to find another set $\{e_i + de_i\}$, then ((10)) applies. Thus de_i is the parameter which shifts from one allowable microstate to another. In the two dimensional case, $de = d pp/2m = p/m dp$, whereas counting momentum states would only involve dp .

As a result, one may argue that for two particles and total energy E , the first particle may have momentum p lying in a range from 0 to $\text{Sqrt}(2m (E))$. If it has a particular momentum value, the

momentum of the second particle is automatically known (1-dimensional motion). The issue is that one may not simply count momentum states in the range 0 to $\sqrt{2mE}$ using dp . Rather, one must use $de_1 + de_2 = 0$, and so de proportional to $p dp$ is used to count the states of particle 1. This leads to a probability $\int_0^{\sqrt{2mE}} p dp$ proportional to E rather than $\int_0^{\sqrt{2mE}} dp$ proportional to \sqrt{E} .

As a result, we argue that states should be counted with respect to the constraint in the problem as this governs equilibrium. If energy is the constraint, as in the Maxwell-Boltzmann gas, then this variable should be used to identify states. Once the probability distribution is found, one may sum over single particle energy in $C \exp(-e/T)$ using momentum states. The momentum states, however, are not at all involved in determining the expression $C \exp(-e/T)$ as ((1)) shows.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the counting of states (associated with probability in statistical mechanics) is not necessarily trivial. States are counted with respect to identifiers, and different identifiers lead to different counts and hence different probabilities. This issue appears even in the straightforward Maxwell-Boltzmann case. If one states that one has N particles with total energy E , there seems to be only one identifier, energy, and one counts states based on it, i.e. $N! / \prod_i n_i!$. Maximizing \ln of this with respect to the constraint $\sum_i e_i n_i = E$ yields the MB distribution $C \exp(-e/T)$. This probability, based on energy state counting, is, however, summed using a counting of states based on a different identifier, namely momentum, i.e. $1 = C \int dp_x dp_y dp_z \exp(-e/T)$. One may ask: Why did one not use momentum to count states in deriving the probability, instead of energy? Why does one count energy states to find $\exp(-e/T)$ and then use a different counting scheme based on momentum to sum over e states?

A second example we present is based on the arguments of (1) and (2). (1) states that probability of an n particle gas (1-dimension) is proportional to the surface area of an $n-1$ sphere which ultimately leads to probability being proportional to $(E-e)$ power $((n-3)/2)$. This is based on the counting of momentum states. (2) counts energy states and finds a probability proportional to $(E-e)$ power $(n-2)$. In the high n limit, one has $(E-e)$ power $(n/2)$ versus $(E-e)$ power n . These are different because they count different states.

We argue that the counting of states should be based on the constraint involved. Consider an energy constraint: $E = \sum_i e_i$. A set $\{e_i\}$ may satisfy this equation. To find a second set, close by, one may use $dE=0 = \sum_i de_i$. Thus $de_i = dp_i/2m = p_i/m dp_i$ is used to count states, i.e. probability is proportional to $\int_0^{\sqrt{2mE}} p dp$ and not: $\int_0^{\sqrt{2mE}} dp$.

References

1. Lopez-Ruiz, R. and Calbet, Z. Why the Maxwell Distribution is the Attractive Fixed Point of the Boltzmann Equation 2006 <https://arxiv.org/pdf/nlin/0611044.pdf>
2. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Speculation on Maxwell-Boltzmann Di

